

Comparison of Early versus Delayed Administration of Furosemide in terms of Improved Oxygenation in Patients with Acute Heart Failure

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Abstract

Objective: The acute heart failure (AHF) which is the rapid onset or severe deterioration of signs & symptoms related to enhanced plasma levels of the natriuretic peptides and most cases present with normal or elevated blood pressure (BP) and along with symptoms of congestion instead of decreased cardiac output. To compare the outcome of early versus delayed administration of furosemide in terms of percentage improved oxygenation in patients with acute heart failure.

Material and Methods: A Quasi-experimental study, Department of Cardiology, Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore (Six months: from 20.9.2022 to 20.3.2023). After meeting inclusion & exclusion criteria, one hundred patients (fifty in one group) were enrolled. The participants were divided into 2 groups: Group-I patients were given furosemide within sixty minutes while Group-II patients were given furosemide after sixty minutes. At baseline, oxygen level was assessed. Then patients were admitted and followed-up in cardiology wards. Oxygen level after 24 hours of furosemide was assessed and percentage improved oxygenation level was noted.

Results: Among 100 patients, mean age was 44.05 ± 11.80 years, 65(65%) patients were male. In early group the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.54 ± 3.89 while among delayed group patients was 7.49 ± 2.69 ($P < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Early administration of furosemide in terms of percentage improved oxygenation showed significantly better outcome as compared to delayed administration in patients with acute heart failure.

Keywords: Acute heart failure, Delayed, Early, Furosemide, Improved oxygenation

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Introduction

The HF (heart failure) is one of the clinical syndromes characterized by a group of symptoms such as orthopnea, dyspnea and swelling of lower limb while signs such as pulmonary congestion and jugular venous elevated pressure often due to functional and/or structural cardiac anomaly resulting in decreased cardiac output and/or intracardiac increased pressures.¹⁻³

However, estimates differ depending upon study population, the heart failure prevalence is about ¹⁻² percent and increases to above 10 percent among individuals aged above 70 years. The acute HF is a lethal condition along with elevated morbidity as well as mortality, that needs emergency medical treatment. Most individuals present with the symptoms of congestion while few of them present with signs of decreased cardiac output.⁴⁻⁵

The acute heart failure (AHF) which is the rapid onset or severe deterioration of signs & symptoms related to enhanced plasma levels of the natriuretic peptides and most cases present with normal or elevated blood pressure (BP) and along with symptoms of congestion instead of decreased cardiac output.⁶⁻⁷

As the individuals suffering from acute myocardial infarction, concept of “time-to-treatment” may be significant; therefore, medical intervention should be started based upon

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BP and/or congestion level utilizing vasodilators and/or diuretics for example, furosemide. The supplemental oxygen should be administered based upon clinical findings unless the oxygen saturation is above 90 percent, in such case, the oxygen therapy must routinely be administered.⁸⁻⁹

It has been observed through a study that improved oxygenation rate was found higher among patients of early group when compared with delayed group [median 16.7 percent (interquartile range: 0.0 to 40.0) versus 0.0 percent (0.0 to 20.6), respectively, $P < 0.001$].¹⁰

The rationale of our study is to compare outcome of early administration of the furosemide with enhanced oxygenation among individuals with acute HF. Through literature, we have observed that furosemide early administration can help to improve oxygenation level in heart failure patients than delayed infusion.

However, only one study had been done before and there is need to conduct more studies to confirm the above stated evidence and improve the current body of knowledge. Also, there is no study done in Pakistan before that may help us in determining the beneficial aspects of furosemide infusion in heart failure patients.

Thus, we plan to perform this study to acquire evidence for local population and improve our knowledge and practice and improve the condition of such critical patients. Appropriate strategies can be planned to overcome the issue of late furosemide administration, which can lead to adverse sequel.

Material and Methods

It was a quasi-experimental study performed at Department of Cardiology, Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore during the period of 6 months i.e. 20.9.2022 to 20.3.2023. Sample size of 100 patients (50 in one group) was calculated with 5% significance level, 80% power of study and percentage of improved oxygenation i.e. 16.7% in early group and 0% in delayed group.¹⁰ non-probability consecutive sampling method was carried out.

Patients aged between 25-65 years of both genders diagnosed with heart failure were included during study. Heart failure was defined as presence of congestion, hyperbilirubinemia (bilirubin > 10 IU), pale yellow skin color, peripheral edema, fluid filled lungs with ejection fraction $< 35\%$ on echocardiography.

Patients with recurrent cases, valvular heart disease, cardiomyopathy, severe hepatic (ALT&AST > 40 IU, hepatitis B and C) or renal dysfunction (Creatinine > 2.0 mg/dl or on dialysis), malignancy, emergency coronary angiography; received pre-hospital furosemide were excluded.

Informed consent was acquired from all participants. Demographic data (such as: age, gender, h/o smoking (> 5 pack years), hypertension (BP $\geq 140/90$ mmHg), hyperlipidemia (total cholesterol > 200 mg/dl), diabetes (BSR > 200 mg/dl), ejection fraction and symptoms duration were noted as well. Then participants were divided into 2 groups: Group-I patients were given furosemide within sixty minutes while Group-II patients were given furosemide after sixty minutes. At baseline, oxygen level (FiO₂) was assessed. Then patients were admitted and followed-up in cardiology wards. Oxygen level after 24 hours of furosemide was assessed and percentage improved oxygenation level was noted. It was calculated by subtracting oxygenation level at baseline from oxygenation level after 24 hours of treatment, then divide this outcome by baseline oxygenation level and multiply with 100. Patients were managed as per standard protocol. All this information was recorded on proforma.

Data was entered and analyzed using computer program SPSS version 25.0. Mean & standard deviation was calculated for the quantitative variables such as age, duration of disease, ejection fraction, oxygen level before and after treatment. Frequency and percentages were calculated for gender, h/o smoking, hypertension (BP $> 160/90$), diabetes (BSR > 200 mg/dl), hyperlipidemia (TC > 200 mg/dl) and percentage improvement on oxygenation. Independent sample t-test was applied to compare percentage improvement in oxygenation level in both groups. P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant. Data was stratified for age, gender, h/o smoking, hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, duration of disease, and ejection fraction. Post-stratification, chi-square test was applied to compare percentage improvement in oxygenation level in both groups in each stratum. P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

Table-1 shows that out of 100 patients enrolled during study, mean age was 44.05 ± 11.80 years with minimum & maximum ages of 25 and 65 years, respectively. In early group (50 patients), mean age was 44.38 ± 11.83 years while in delayed group was 43.72 ± 11.88 years ($P = 0.781$).

Among these patients 65(65%) were male and 35(35%) were females. In early group 39(78%) patients were male and in delayed group 26(52%) patients were male ($P = 0.006$).

The mean BMI of patients was 25.61 ± 5.06 kg/m² with minimum & maximum BMI of 18 and 34.93 kg/m², respectively. In early group, patients mean BMI was 25.51 ± 5.14 kg/m² while in delayed group was 25.71 ± 5.03 kg/m² ($P = 0.841$).

The mean duration of heart failure of patients was 11.82 ± 6.34 days with minimum & maximum values of 1.00 and 24.00 days, respectively. In early group, mean duration of heart

failure of participants was 11.86 ± 6.57 days and in delayed group was 11.78 ± 6.17 days ($P=0.950$).

The mean duration of ejection fraction of the participants was 27.47 ± 4.87 with minimum & maximum values of 35.00 and 24.00, respectively. In early group, mean ejection fraction of participants was 27.44 ± 4.69 and in delayed group was 27.50 ± 5.08 ($P=0.951$).

At baseline, mean oxygenation value of participants was 84.69 ± 3.22 and after treatment its mean value was 92.68 ± 3.12 . At baseline, in early group, mean oxygenation value of participants was 84.32 ± 3.16 while in delayed group was 85.06 ± 3.28 ($p\text{-value}=0.253$). After treatment, in early group, mean oxygenation value of participants was 93.98 ± 3.10 while in delayed group was 91.38 ± 2.59 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$).

The mean value of percentage improvement in oxygenation of the patients was 9.52 ± 3.90 with minimum & maximum values of 1.11 and 20.00 days, respectively. In early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of participants was 11.54 ± 3.89 and in delayed group was 7.49 ± 2.69 ($P<0.001$).

Table-2 describes that among patients aged ≤ 50 years; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.90 ± 4.78 while in delayed group was 7.77 ± 1.36 ($p\text{-value}=0.046$). Among patients aged >50 years; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.47 ± 3.77 and in delayed group was 7.44 ± 2.91 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$).

Among male patients; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.49 ± 4.23 and in delayed group was 7.30 ± 2.95 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$). Among female patients; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.69 ± 2.54 and in delayed group was 7.71 ± 2.42 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$).

Among patients with BMI $\leq 25\text{kg/m}^2$; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.71 ± 3.97 while in delayed group was 7.17 ± 2.82 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$). Among patients with BMI $>25\text{kg/m}^2$; in early group, mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 10.99 ± 3.76 and in delayed group was 8.41 ± 2.12 ($p\text{-value}=0.052$).

In patients having duration of HF ≤ 12 days; in early group the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.85 ± 3.84 and in delayed group was 7.24 ± 2.48 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$). In patients having duration of HF >12 days; in early group the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 11.17 ± 4.02 and in delayed group was 7.73 ± 2.89 ($p\text{-value}=0.001$).

In patients having ejection fraction ≤ 30 ; in early group the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients

was 12.32 ± 3.54 while in delayed group was 7.05 ± 2.78 ($p\text{-value}<0.001$). In patients having ejection fraction >30 ; in early group the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of patients was 10.13 ± 4.21 and in delayed group was 8.30 ± 2.38 ($p\text{-value}=0.118$).

Figure 1: Comparison of gender between study groups

Table 1: Comparison of study variables between study groups

	Total Patients <i>n</i> = 100	Study Groups		P-value
		Early <i>n</i> = 50	Delayed <i>n</i> = 50	
Age (years), mean±SD	44.05±11.80	44.38±11.83	43.72±11.88	0.781
Gender, n (%)	65 (65.0%)	39 (78.0%)	26 (52.0%)	0.006
Male	35 (35.0%)	11 (22.0%)	24 (48.0%)	
Female				
BMI (kg/m²), mean±SD	25.61±5.06	25.51±5.14	25.71±5.03	0.841
Duration of heart failure (months), mean±SD	11.82±6.34	11.86±6.57	11.78±6.17	0.950
Ejection fraction, mean±SD	27.47±4.87	27.44±4.69	27.50±5.08	0.951
Oxygenation, mean±SD	84.69±3.22	84.32±3.16	85.06±3.28	0.253
Baseline	92.68±3.12	93.98±3.10	91.38±2.59	
After treatment				<0.001
Percentage improvement, mean±SD	9.52±3.90	11.54±3.89	7.49±2.69	<0.001

Table 2: Comparison of percentage improvement in oxygenation between study groups stratified by age, gender, BMI, duration of HF and ejection fraction

	Study Group	Percentage Improvement			p-value
		n	Mean	SD	
Age (years)	≤ 50	Early	8	11.90	0.046
	Delayed	9	7.77	1.36	

		d			6	
Gender	>50	Early	4 2	11.4 7	3.7 7	<0.001
		Delayed	4 1	7.44 1	2.9 1	
	Male	Early	3 9	11.4 9	4.2 3	<0.001
		Delayed	2 6	7.30 5	2.9 5	
Female	Early	1 1	11.6 9	2.5 4	<0.001	
	Delayed	2 4	7.71 2	2.4 2		
BMI (kg/m ²)	≤ 25	Early	3 8	11.7 1	3.9 7	<0.001
		Delayed	3 7	7.17 2	2.8 2	
	>25	Early	1 2	10.9 9	3.7 6	0.052
		Delayed	1 3	8.41 2	2.1 2	
Duration of HF (days)	≤ 12	Early	2 7	11.8 5	3.8 4	<0.001
		Delayed	2 4	7.24 8	2.4 8	
	>12	Early	2 3	11.1 7	4.0 2	0.001
		Delayed	2 6	7.73 9	2.8 9	
Ejection fraction	≤ 30	Early	3 2	12.3 2	3.5 4	<0.001
		Delayed	3 2	7.05 8	2.7 8	
	>30	Early	1 8	10.1 3	4.2 1	0.118
		Delayed	1 8	8.30 8	2.3 8	

used for the treatment of HF by reducing the amount of fluid in the body.¹¹⁻¹³

Our study revealed that in early group, the mean percentage improvement in oxygenation of participants was 11.54±3.89 while in delayed group was 7.49±2.69 (p-value=<0.001). Several studies have evaluated the effect of furosemide early administration on oxygenation among patients with AHF. Here are some of the studies and their findings.

One study by Takafumi Mikami et al. resulted that early administration cohort included 121 (55.3%) patients. The improved oxygenation rate was found high among patients of early cohort than non-early cohort [median 16.7 percent (interquartile range: 0.0 to 40.0) versus 0.0 percent (0.0 to 20.6), respectively, P<0.001]. In this, the in-hospital mortality rate was 5.0% (6 patients) in early cohort while 9.2% (9 patients) in non-early cohort. The cardiac death was noticed less commonly in early cohort than in non-early cohort, but with no statistical significance (3.3 & 9.2 percent, respectively) (P=0.067).¹⁰

A meta-analysis conducted by Rodrigues et al. (2024) evaluated the effect of door-to-IV diuretic time on mortality rate among individuals with AHF. The pooled estimations from the observational studies including 28,124 participants, early IV furosemide was related to a 23 percent decrease in the 30-day mortality in acute HF, despite no significant in-hospital death reduction.¹⁴

Ward and colleagues (2018) conducted a study among patients presented to emergency department and received a dosage of intravenous furosemide. Study highlighted that every 60-minute delay in furosemide IV administration was related to 8 percent lower rate of successful discharge home when compared with someone who was administered with early furosemide.¹⁵

However, no evidence is found regarding evident mechanism underlying relationship between the shorter D2F and in-hospital better survival, a study reported that how the early therapy can avert worsening myocardial as well as other organ damage during acute phase of heart failure, after that improving the in-hospital outcomes.¹⁶ A RELAX-AHF study and one sub-study demonstrated that early therapy of acute HF with serelaxin was related to dyspnea improvement and prevention of enhanced high-sensitivity troponin during acute phase as well as better survival.¹⁷

An observational study demonstrated that IV furosemide early administration was related to in-hospital lower mortality and HF current guideline in Japan suggests that treatment should be started as early as possible.¹⁸⁻¹⁹

In a randomized controlled trial (RCT) by Matsue et al, 212 patients with AHF were randomly assigned to receive either early intravenous furosemide within 1 hour of admission (early group) or standard care (delayed group). The early group showed a significantly greater improvement in oxygenation (as measured by the PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio) at 6 hours

Figure 2: Comparison of oxygenation between study groups

Discussion

The heart failure is an important clinical disorder that occurs due to inability of heart to pump sufficient blood to fulfill the body's metabolic requirements. One of the key symptoms of HF is the accumulation of fluid in the lungs, which can cause shortness of breath and decreased oxygenation. Furosemide is a loop diuretic that is commonly

compared to the delayed group ($p=0.005$).²⁰ Another study by Gheorghiadu et al. examined the effect of furosemide early administration among patients with acute decompensated HF. During study 1420 individuals were enrolled and randomized to receive either furosemide early administration (within 60 minutes of health facility arrival) or delayed administration (more than 60 minutes after arrival). The study primary endpoint was the change in dyspnea score at 6 hours after treatment.²¹

A systematic review done by Muzammil and colleagues (2025) assessed numerous studies evaluating the i/v loop diuretics timing in acute decompensated HF. This review found that the diuretics early administration during first 60 to 90 minutes after arrival in hospital was mostly linked to improved outcomes, including better decongestion as well as decrease mortality rate among some cohorts. Study results indicated that prompt diuretic treatments help in achieving faster removal of pulmonary fluid that contributes to better oxygenation as well as symptomatic relief among individuals with acute HF.²²

A meta-analysis was performed by Tariq and coworkers (2024) to analyze the data from 6 observational studies in which 20,000 individuals with acute HF were included. The study investigated the impact of door-to-diuretic time ≤ 60 min vs late administration. However, mortality differences were found insignificant, authors emphasized that early diuretic treatment supports faster decongestion as well as clinical stabilization, which could help in improving the respiratory symptoms and oxygenation among individuals with pulmonary edema.²³

Marques and his colleagues (2023) examined the relationship between door-to-furosemide time and clinical outcomes among individuals with acute HF. Patients receiving i/v furosemide within 1 hour of the hospital arrival had considerably lower short-term risks of HF hospitalization and cardiovascular death compared with those receiving delayed treatment.²⁴

Huang and associates (2022) undertook a study in which ten studies with 775 individuals (338 receiving furosemide continuous administration & 387 receiving furosemide intermittent administration) were included. Study demonstrated important differences in the weight loss and 24-hour urine volume between two groups. No significant difference was noticed regarding duration of hospital stay and all-cause mortality.²⁵

A retrospective single-center cohort study was performed by Viriyanukulvong et al. (2021) among 820 patients with acute HF. Study highlighted that median D2F time was 80.5 minutes. Among 39.0% (324) patients who were categorized in early D2F time group, total in-hospital mortality rate was 4.9 percent and did not vary between the groups (early group 3.1% versus 6% delayed group). Study indicated that early administration is not significantly related to lower in-hospital mortality.²⁶

There have been several studies investigating the outcome of furosemide early administration with improved oxygenation among individuals with acute HF. One such study conducted by Matsue et al. in which one hundred patients with acute HF were enrolled and randomized to either receive furosemide early administration (within one hour of hospital arrival) or standard care (administration of furosemide after initial stabilization). The study primary outcome was improvement in oxygenation at 6 hours after hospitalization, as measured by ratio of arterial oxygen tension to inspired oxygen fraction (PaO_2/FiO_2).¹⁸

Overall, these studies suggest that early administration of furosemide in patients with AHF is related to a greater improvement in oxygenation compared to delayed administration. However, the percentage improvement in oxygenation varies across studies and may be influenced by various factors such as patient characteristics and study design. However, further studies are required to ratify these findings and to determine the optimal timing and dosing of furosemide administration in this patient population.

Conclusion

Study concluded that early administration of furosemide in terms of percentage improved oxygenation showed significantly better outcome as compared to delayed administration in patients with acute heart failure.

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Author's contribution:

SM, BW: Conceptualization of Project

SM, BW, AM: Data Collection

BW, AM: Literature Search

SM, BW: Statistical Analysis

SM, BW, AM: Drafting, Revision

SM: Writing of Manuscript